

Impact of Digital Advertisements on Consumer E-Consumption Behavior

Komal Mehreen¹ Robina Roshan²

ABSTRACT: The study investigates the evolving trends in consumer online consumption behaviors in the digital age. Its primary objective is to assess the impact of digital advertisements on consumers' e-consumption behavior, with a specific focus on the consumption values influenced by various digital advertising strategies. To explore this phenomenon, the study adopted a survey methodology, utilizing the Theory of Consumption Value as a theoretical framework. The sample consists of 1,270 students from the top six public sector universities in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP), Pakistan. Data was collected through a self-constructed, close-ended questionnaire. The analysis of the collected data indicates that a significant percentage of respondents engage with digital advertisements, with many reporting that they frequently encounter floating ads on social media platforms. Furthermore, the findings reveal that the majority of respondents prefer online consumption methods, citing it as the most effective way to discover the products/services they need. Additionally, a notable number of respondents indicated that their online consumption behavior is motivated by a desire for social recognition and fame among their peers.

KEYWORDS: Digital Advertisements, Consumer, E-Consumption Behavior

¹ PhD Scholar, Department of Communication & Media Studies, Gomal University Dera Ismail Khan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Email: [komalmehreen21@gmail.com](mailto:komalmehtreen21@gmail.com)

² Assistant Professor, Department of Communication and Media Studies, Gomal University Dera Ismail Khan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Email: robina.roshan@yahoo.com

Corresponding Author: Komal Mehreen

✉ [komalmehreen21@gmail.com](mailto:komalmehtreen21@gmail.com)

Introduction

Advertising plays a crucial role in influencing consumer behavior, as it has the potential to shape consumer perceptions, attitudes, and purchase decisions (Smith, 2019; Jones et al., 2020). With the ever-increasing presence of advertisements in our daily lives, understanding the impact of advertising on consumer behavior has become a vital area of research in marketing and consumer psychology. The primary objective of this study is to examine the relationship between digital advertising and consumer e-consumption behavior, specifically focusing on the various dimensions of consumer behavior influenced by advertising strategies. There is a dearth of research examining the influence of digital advertising on consumer behavior, which is increasingly relevant in the digital age.

E-business is gaining substantial strength and has become an essential component of overall business practices. Advertisers can use Internet advertising to target audiences selectively and precisely by placing attractive ads on results pages, search engine, vlogs, blogs, online classified ads, etc. Studies have shown that digital advertising can increase marketing effectiveness when used in conjunction with TV, print, and other

traditional media (Koetsier, 2014). Researchers report that because of digital media now world become a global village and people are more connected than ever. Consequently, internet usage and related technologies will continue to grow faster across all product and service categories (Constantinides,, 2014; Deighton & Kornfeld, 2009).

The Internet provides an effective method for reaching a larger market than traditional methods. Using the internet and related technologies, businesses can enhance their market presence both virtually and physically at every stage of the consumer e-consumption process. Additionally, to enhance brand awareness, digital media can effectively influence consumer attitudes and consumption behavior (Aaker, 2003; Keller, 2003

Problem Statement

The current study investigates the impact of digital advertising on consumer e-consumption behavior.

Significance of the Study

A significant finding of this research study shows that digital advertising has taken on a whole new dimension, and consumers have more choices to satisfy their needs than ever before. This study is beneficial in a way that it will explore the new ways and factors that would help advertisers create mass brand awareness, create new platforms for consumers to interact with the brand and other consumers, and provide consumers with a means of researching different products/ services in online environments. Moreover, the current study is extremely useful to advertisers in understanding consumer choices that influence their online consumption patterns.

Research Objectives

1. To investigate different demographic variables i.e., gender, age, qualification, residential status, and monthly income of consumers.
2. To investigate the frequency of watching digital advertisements by consumers
3. To explore the medium used by consumers to watch digital advertisements
4. To explore different kinds of digital advertisements preferred by consumers.
5. To examine the effect of digital advertising on consumers' e-consumption behavior.

Hypothesis of the Study

1. **H₁**: There is a significant difference between different demographic variables (gender, age, qualification, residential status, and monthly income) of the respondents and exposure to digital advertisements.
2. **H₂**: Higher the exposure to digital advertisements, the higher will be its impact on consumers' e-consumption behavior.

Literature Review

Digital Advertising

According to Park and Kim, (2012), digital advertising is an effective way of delivering promotional messages to prospective consumers using the Internet. According to another study done by Miller, (2012), digital

advertising is a complex process of using advertising techniques and the latest technology to make advertisements more appealing like TV ads. Today as consumers use digital tools and networks more than before, digital advertising is the most suitable way to reach and affect them. According to Sheng and Gao, Sheng (2013). Following are some of the prominent features and advantages of digital advertising,

- ▶ Digital advertising is the best platform for two-way communication between brands and consumers.
- ▶ Due to digital advertising consumers are directly connected with the brand.
- ▶ To promote both static and dynamic advertisement choice, representation, and display, digital advertisers can use customer targeting methods.
- ▶ Digital advertisements are available to the global audience 24/7.
- ▶ Because of their online nature, digital advertisements can be easily modified.
- ▶ Digital advertisements are extremely monitorable and evaluable.

Effects of Digital Advertisements on Customers E-Consumption Behavior

According to McElfresh, C.; Mineiro, & Rodford, (2007) techniques used for digital advertising such as pop-up ads, floating ads, email ads, and pop-under ads are sometimes irritating for internet users. Interestingly for a long time, Television commercials have also been criticized by experts as the leader in advertising annoyance. However, research indicated that online consumers are more goal-oriented and judge online advertisements even more harshly than those in other media. The negative perception that users develop towards intrusive ads leads them to not return to that website. A Jupiter Research survey showed that 69% of users consider pop-ups annoying, and, further, 23% said they would not return to the site simply because of the ads (McElfresh, C.; Mineiro, & Rodford, 2007) with users needing instant gratification not being able to complete their goals while online is starting to diminish their feelings toward advertisements, company brands, and website environments. Abernethy describes intrusive online ads as being a television viewer who cannot leave the room or change the channel during a commercial, the user feels helpless because there is little they can do to escape these ads other than interrupt their task, scroll past ads, or close the pop-up/pop-under windows.

Theoretical Framework

The Theory of Consumption Values (TVC)

Why We Buy What We Buy; The Theory of Consumption Values (TVC) is the prominent model used to explain consumer decision-making. The model consists of five key values that play a vital role in influencing consumer choices such as functional, emotional, social, epistemic, and conditional values, which can anticipate consumer choices while buying any product or service. TVC has been adopted by different researchers to explain technology adoption and consumer behavior in the digital age such as food delivery apps (Chakraborty, 2022a; Kaur, 2021; Tandon, 2021), online brands (Fathima et al., 2022), over-the-top platforms (Talwar, 2024), live streaming services (Singh, 2021), Buying services from online travel agencies (Talwar, 2020) and augmented reality in retail (Wang, 2023). According to Teng, (2018) five values of TVC are helpful in explaining consumer future purchase intentions which are related to both usage and ongoing usage intentions (Sharma et al., 2022). TCV-based studies indicate that all consumption values significantly influence consumer choices (e.g., Du, 2021; Suki, 2022).

Methodology

Research methodology refers to the systematic and logical approach used to conduct research and collect data to answer research questions or test hypotheses. It involves the selection of appropriate methods, techniques, and procedures to gather and analyze information in a reliable and valid manner. Research methodology enables the researchers to study the phenomena systematically. Research design involves determining the plan and structure of the study. It includes decisions regarding the research approach (quantitative, qualitative, or mixed methods), research setting, selection of participants, and the overall framework for data collection and analysis. This research was quantitative in nature therefore; the researcher used a survey research design to investigate and explore the impact of digital advertisements on consumer consumption patterns. The population for this study comprised the students of the top six public sector universities of KP, Pakistan namely the University of Engineering and Technology Peshawar, University of Peshawar, Gomal University, University of Swat, Kohat University of Science and Technology, and Hazara University Mansehra. For the current study, students of the top six public sector universities of KP, Pakistan comprised the unit of analysis. Furthermore, the researcher used a multi-stage stratified sampling technique for sample selection. The sample size for this study comprised 1270. The self-constructed questionnaire was used for data collection. Likert scale questions were added to the questionnaire to get the responses from the respondents and easy for them to fill out the questionnaire. Data was analyzed using basic descriptive statistics including frequency, percentage, and Mean. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), Simple Linear Regression, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

Results

Section-I: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1

Gender of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	771	60.7%
Female	499	39.3%
Total	1270	100.0%

Table 1 reveals the information of respondents from the perspective of gender. The table shows that there are 499 (39.3%) female respondents and 771(60.7%) male respondents included in the study. Thus, overall, 1270 respondents contributed to the present research work.

Table 2

Age of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
21-30	717	56.5%
31-40	479	37.7%
Above 40	74	5.8%
Total	1270	100.0%

Table 2 reveals the information of respondents from the perspective of age. The table shows that there are 717 (56.5%) respondents with age ranging 21-30 years, 479 (37.7%) respondents with age ranging 31-40

years, and 74 (5.8%) respondents with age above 40 years participated in the study. Thus, overall, 1270 respondents with different age groups contributed to the present research work.

Table 3

Qualification of the Respondents

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Undergraduate	613	48.3%
Master	507	39.9%
MS/MPhil/PhD	150	11.8%
Total	1270	100.0%

Table 3 reveals the information of respondents from the perspective of qualification. The table shows that 613 (48.3%) respondents had undergraduate, 507 (39.9%) respondents had master's degrees, and 150 (11.8%) respondents are with MS/MPhil/PhD degrees included in the study. Thus, overall, 1270 respondents with different educational backgrounds contributed to the research work.

Table 4

Residential Status of the Respondents

Residential Status	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Urban	718	56.5%
Rural	552	43.5%
Total	1270	100.0%

Table 4 reveals the information of respondents in perspective of residential status. The table shows that 718 (65.5%) respondents are from urban and 552 (43.5%) respondents are from rural areas.

Table 5

Monthly Income of the Respondents

Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Below 20 thousand	280	22.0%
21 to 30 thousand	749	59.0%
31 to 40 thousand	170	13.4%
Above 40 thousand	71	5.6%
Total	1270	100.0%

Table 5 reveals the information of respondents from the perspective of monthly income. The table shows that 280 (22.0%) respondents were below 20 thousand, 749 (59.0%) respondents were monthly income in between the range of 21-30 thousand, 170 (13.4%) respondents were monthly income ranging from 21 thousand to 40 thousand and 71 (5.6%) respondents were monthly income were ranging more than 40 thousand included in the study. Thus, overall, 1270 respondents contributed to the research work.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 6

Frequency of Watching Digital Advertisements

Statistics	Never	Rarely	Sometime	Frequently	Very Frequently	Mean Score
F	204	531	222	207	106	2.59
%	16.1%	41.8%	17.5%	16.3%	8.3%	

Table 6 indicates the descriptive Statistics (frequency and percentage) of the frequency of watching digital advertisements. The result reveals that 41.8% of respondents rarely watch digital advertisements (Mean=2.59).

Table 7

Frequency of Using Different Digital Mediums for Watching Digital Advertisements

Categories	Statistics	Never	Rarely	Sometime	Often	Very Often	Mean Score
SMS	F	188	322	130	354	276	2.16
	%	14.8%	25.4%	10.2%	27.9%	21.7%	
Email	f	108	719	321	102	20	2.37
	%	8.5%	56.6%	25.3%	8.0%	1.6%	
Search Engines	f	186	761	161	132	30	2.25
	%	14.6%	59.9%	12.7%	10.4%	2.4%	
Mobile App	f	235	688	183	102	62	2.26
	%	18.5%	54.2%	14.4%	8.0%	4.9%	

Table 7 indicates the descriptive Statistics (frequency and percentage) of watching digital advertisements using different digital mediums such as social media sites, e-mail, search engines, and mobile apps. The result reveals that the majority of respondents (25.4%) rarely use social media sites (Mean=2.16), 56.6% of respondents rarely use email (Mean=2.37), 59.9% rarely use search engines (Mean=2.25) and 54.2% respondents rarely use mobile app (Mean=2.26) for watching digital advertisement.

Table 8

Frequency of Watching Different Kinds of Digital Ads

Categories	Statistics	Never	Rarely	Sometime	Often	Very Often	Mean Score
Floating ads	f	628	315	189	70	68	1.92
	%	49.4%	24.8%	14.9%	5.5%	5.4%	
E-mail ads	f	391	501	237	105	36	2.12
	%	30.8%	39.4%	18.7%	8.3%	2.8%	
Pop-up ads	f	331	579	189	129	42	2.19
	%	26.1%	45.6%	14.9%	10.2%	3.3%	
Video ads	f	264	527	131	258	90	2.51
	%	20.8%	41.5%	10.3%	20.3%	7.1%	
Pay-Per-Click ads	f	293	469	262	122	124	2.46
	%	23.1%	26.9%	20.6%	9.6%	9.8%	
Animated ads	f	177	472	137	229	255	2.93
	%	13.9%	37.2%	10.8%	18.0%	20.1%	

Table 8 indicates the descriptive Statistics (frequency and percentage) about the frequency of watching different kinds of digital ads such as floating ads, e-mail ads, Pop-up ads, video ads, Pay-per-click, and animated ads. The result reveals the majority of respondents (49.1%) very never watch floating ads (Mean=1.93), 39.4% of respondents rarely watch email ads (Mean=2.12), 45.6% rarely watch pop-up ads (Mean=2.19), 41.5% respondents rarely watch video-ads (Mean=2.2.51), 26.9% rarely watch pay-per click ads (Mean=2.46) and 37.2% respondents rarely watch animated ads (Mean=2.93).

Table 9

Time Spend on Watching Digital Advertisements by the Respondents

Statistics	30 Minutes	1-Hour	2-Hour	Mean Score
f	512	696	62	1.64
%	40.3%	54.8%	4.9%	

Table 9 indicates the descriptive Statistics (frequency and percentage) about spending time watching digital advertisements. The result reveals that 54.8% of respondents spent one hour while 40.3% respondents spent only half an hour watching digital advertisements (Mean=1.64).

Table 10

Frequency of Consumer's E-Consumption Behavior

Categories	Statistic s	Never	Rarely	Sometime	often	Very Often	Mean Score
Online is the best way to find the product I need.	f %	402 31.7%	343 27.0%	245 19.3%	111 8.7%	169 13.3%	2.45
I buy things online because I want to become famous among others	f %	111 8.7%	595 46.9%	278 21.9%	141 11.1%	145 11.4%	2.69
Sometimes cost of consuming online products has unsatisfactory results.	f %	213 16.8%	639 50.3%	154 12.1%	114 9.0%	150 11.8%	2.48
The benefit of shopping online is that I can view a variety of products with a single click to save time	f %	254 20.0%	505 39.8%	204 16.1%	141 11.1%	166 13.1%	2.57
Online reviews give me an immediate and clear picture of people's reactions regarding certain products.	f %	568 44.7%	251 19.8%	171 13.5%	111 8.7%	169 13.3%	2.26
Digital advertising helps me realize the value and importance of certain products	f %	163 12.8%	446 35.1%	199 15.7%	250 19.7%	212 16.7%	2.92

Table 10 indicates the consumer's e-consumption behavior. The result indicates that 31.7% respondents don't believe that online is the best way to find the product that they need (Mean=2.45). 46.9% of respondents rarely buy things online because they want to become famous among others (Mean=2.68). 50.3% of respondents have thought that rarely the cost of consuming online products is having unsatisfactory results (Mean=2.48). 39.8% of respondents thought that rarely the benefit of shopping online is that they can view a variety of products on a single click to save time (Mean=2.57). 44.7% of respondents don't believe that reviews give them an immediate and clear picture of people's reactions regarding certain products (Mean=2.26). 35.1% of respondents are of the view that digital advertisements rarely help them realize the value and importance of certain products (Mean=2.92).

Inferential Statistics

H₁: There is a significant difference between different demographic variables of the respondents and exposure to digital advertisements

Table 11

H_{1.1} Showing the Mean difference in respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisements from the perspective of gender

Gender	n	Mean	SD	t-cal	p-value
Male	771	2.5191	.79464	4.99	.000
Female	499	2.3268	.57892		

Table 11 reveals the mean difference in the respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisement from the perspective of gender. The result depicts that the Mean scores of Males and females are estimated at 2.51 and 2.32 respectively. Moreover, the t-cal value was estimated at 4.99 with p=.001<.05 which indicates that a significant difference was found in the respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisements from the perspective of gender.

Table 12

H_{1.2} Showing the Mean difference in respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisements in perspective of Qualification

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	50.984	2	25.492	59.508	.000
Within Groups	542.757	1267	.428		
Total	593.741	1269			

Table 12 reveals the mean difference in the respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisement from the perspective of qualification. The result depicts that the value F=59.508 which shows that the difference among the group means is significantly greater than the variability within each group. Moreover, the value p=.000<.05 indicates that a significant difference was found in the respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisements from the perspective of qualification.

Table 13

H_{1.3} Showing the Mean difference in respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisements from the perspective of Age

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2.762	2	1.381	2.961	.052
Within Groups	590.979	1267	.466		
Total	593.741	1269			

Table 13 reveals the mean difference in the respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisement from the perspective of Age. The result depicts that the value F=2.96 which shows that the difference among the group means is similar to variability within each group. Moreover, the value $p=.052 > .05$ indicates that no significant difference was found in the respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisements from the perspective of the age group.

Table 14

H_{1.4} Showing the Mean difference in respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisements in perspective of Residential Status

Locality	n	Mean	SD	t-cal	p-value
Urban	718	2.6229	.72299	13.72	.000
Rural	552	2.1270	.50801		

Table 14 reveals the mean difference in the respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisements from the perspective of residential status. The result depicts that the Mean score of urban and rural respondents' views was estimated at 2.62 and 2.12 respectively. Moreover, the t-cal value was estimated at 13.72 with $p=.000 < .05$ which indicates that a significant difference was found in the respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisements from the perspective of residential status.

Table 15

H_{1.5} Showing the Mean difference in respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisements in perspective of monthly Income

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	44.572	3	14.857	34.251	.000
Within Groups	549.169	1266	.434		
Total	593.741	1269			

Table 15 reveals the mean difference in the respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisements from the perspective of monthly income. The result depicts that the value F=34.251 which shows that the difference among the group means is significantly greater than the variability within each group. Moreover, the value $p=.000 < .05$ indicates that a significant difference was found in the respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisements from the perspective of monthly income.

H₂ Higher the exposure to digital advertising, the higher will be its impact on consumers' e-consumption behavior.

Table 16

Showing the model summary of Exposure of Digital Advertisements and Consumer's E-Consumption Behavior

R	R ²	Adjusted- R ²	F-value	B	Sig.	D-W
.758 ^a	.575	.575	1715.30	.758	.000	1.55

a. Predictors: (Constant), Exposure to Digital Advertisements

b. Dependent Variable: Consumers E-Consumption Behavior

Table 16 shows the overall regression summary regarding the impact of Exposure to Digital Advertisements on Consumer's E-Consumption Behaviors. The result reveals that $R=.758$ and $R\text{-Square}=.575$ which depicts that 57.5% variation occurred in the dependent variable Consumer e-consumption behavior due to predictor exposure to digital advertisements. Moreover, the value of $F=1715.30$ shows the model's fitness and supports the evidence for the rejection null hypothesis. The value $p=.000<.05$ which indicates there is a significant impact of Exposure to Digital Advertisements on Consumer's E-Consumption Behavior. The positive beta value indicates that if a single unit increases in predictor, then .758 SD unit will be increased in dependent variable consumer e-consumption behavior. The Durban-Watson score (1.55) shows that no autocorrelation existed between the variables.

Conclusion

Analysis of the study reveals that the majority of the respondents are male while a small number of respondents are female. Results indicate that a big percentage of respondents are from the 21-30 years age limit, while a small percentage of respondents are from above the 40 years age limit. Findings also indicate that the majority of the respondents belong to the undergraduate level of education, a small number of respondents are from the MS/MPhil/PhD level of education. Research findings also demonstrate that most of the respondents belong to urban areas. According to the study findings, most of the respondent's monthly income is between the range of 21-30 thousand, while a small number of respondents earn more than 40 thousand per month. The study concluded that the majority of the respondents use social media sites for watching digital advertisements while a small number of respondents prefer mobile apps to watch digital ads. The study concluded that most of the respondents never watch online floating ads and few respondents like to watch online video advertisements. It is also deduced that a big percentage of respondents like to watch online animated and pay-per-click ads while a small percentage of respondents watch pop-up advertisements. The study also concluded that most of the respondents spend 1 hour watching digital advertisements while a small number of the respondents spend 30 minutes. It is concluded that a small percentage of respondents find online methods as the best way to find the product to gratify their needs and the majority of the respondents buy online products to become famous among others. The research also indicated that the majority of the respondents are not satisfied with the results of online products and online reviews. It is also concluded that a big percentage of respondents agreed with the statement that online shopping is the best way to find different products/ services and the best way to save time while a small percentage of respondents agreed with the statement that digital advertising helps them in understanding the value and importance of certain products.

This research study included six hypotheses (Sub-Hypothesis) which were tested using inferential statistics. The findings showed that a significant difference was found in the respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisements in perspective of gender, qualification, residential status, and monthly income while findings reveal that no significant difference was found in the respondents' views regarding exposure to digital advertisements in perspective of age group. Findings of the overall regression summary regarding the impact of Exposure to Digital Advertisements on Consumer's E-Consumption Behavior also indicate there is a significant impact of Exposure to Digital Advertisements on Consumer's E-Consumption Behavior and there is no autocorrelation exists between the variables.

Recommendations/Direction for Future Research

The following recommendations are given for the future researcher

1. The present study was conducted in the context of KP, Pakistan. Future research should be conducted in other areas of the county to see whether the findings of the present study are applicable or not.
2. The present research was conducted using a qualitative method of research using close-ended questionnaires as a data collection tool. Future researchers should adopt a mixed methodology for in-depth investigation of the current phenomena.
3. Future researchers can also include psychological and cultural aspects influencing consumer e-consumption behavior.

Reference

- Aaker, D. A. (2004). Leveraging the Corporate Brand. *California Management Review*, 46(3), 6-18. <https://doi.org/10.1177/000812560404600301>
- Chakraborty, D., Kayal, G., Mehta, P., Nunkoo, R. and Rana, N.P. (2022a), "Consumers' usage of food delivery app: a theory of consumption values", *Journal of Hospitality Marketing and Management*, 31(5), 601-619, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19368623.2022.2024476>
- Constantinides, E. (2014) Foundations of Social Media Marketing. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 148, 40-57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.07.016>
- Deighton, John & Kornfeld, Leora, 2009. "Interactivity's Unanticipated Consequences for Marketers and Marketing," *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, Elsevier, 23(1), 4-10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2008.10.001>
- Du, C. T., NGO, T. T., Tran, T. V., & Nguyen, N. B. T. (2021). Consumption value, consumer innovativeness, and new product adoption: Empirical evidence from Vietnam. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(3), 1275-1286. <https://doi.org/10.13106/jafeb.2021.vol8.no3.1275>
- Fathima, M.S.A., Khan, A. and Alam, A.S. (2022), "Relationship of the theory of consumption values and flow with online brand experience: a study of Young consumers", *Journal of Internet Commerce*, Vol. ahead-of-print ahead-of-print, pp. 1-29, <https://doi.org/10.1080/15332861.2022.2109876>.
- Gao, J., Sheng, B. Chang, L., and Shim, S. (2013). *Online Advertising - Taxonomy and Engineering Perspectives*, San Jose State University.
- Jones, C., (2020) "Advertising and the Way Forward", *Westminster Papers in Communication and Culture* 15(2), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.16997/wpcc.392>
- Kaur, P., Dhir, A., Talwar, S. and Ghuman, K. (2021), "The value proposition of food delivery apps from the perspective of the theory of consumption value", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, Vol. 33 No. 4, pp. 1129-1159,; <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-05-2020-0477>
- Keller, K. L. (2003). Understanding Brands, Branding and Brand Equity. *Interactive Marketing*, 5, 7-20. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.im.4340213>
- Kim, S. and Park, H. (2012) Effects of Various Characteristics of Social Commerce (S-Commerce) on Consumers' Trust and Trust Performance. *International Journal of Information Management*, 33, 318-332. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2012.11.006>
- Koetsier, J. (2014). Digital advertising hits \$43 B, passing broadcast TV for the first time ever. *Internet Advertising Bureau*.
- Miller, R. K. (2012). *The 2012 Entertainment, Media & Advertising Market Research*. Handbook. 12th Edition
- Sharma, T. G., Hamari, J., Kesharwani, A., & Tak, P. (2022). Understanding continuance intention to play online games: roles of self-expressiveness, self-congruity, self-efficacy, and perceived risk. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 41(2), 348-364. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144929X.2020.1811770>
- Singh, S., Singh, N., Kalinić, Z., & Liébana-Cabanillas, F. J. (2021). Assessing determinants influencing continued use of live streaming services: An extended perceived value theory of streaming addiction. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 168, 114241. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2020.114241>
- Smith, M. (2019). *Research Methods in Accounting (5th ed.)*. SAGE Publications Limited

- Suki, M.N., Majeed, A. and Suki, M.N. (2022), "Impact of consumption values on consumers' purchase of organic food and green environmental concerns", *Social Responsibility Journal*, 18(6), 1128-1141, <https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-01-2021-0026>
- Talwar, S., Dhir, A., Kaur, P., & Mäntymäki, M. (2020). Why do people purchase from online travel agencies (OTAs)? A consumption values perspective. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 88, 102534. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102534>
- Talwar, S., Kaur, P., Kumar, S., Laroche, M., & Dhir, A. (2024). Caged, helpless but not bored: consumption values derived from over-the-top platforms during pandemic. *Information Technology & People*, 37(1), 422-448. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITP-11-2021-0837>
- Tandon, A., Kaur, P., Bhatt, Y., Mäntymäki, M., & Dhir, A. (2021). Why do people purchase from food delivery apps? A consumer value perspective. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 63, 102667. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2021.102667>
- Teng, C. I. (2018). Look to the future: Enhancing online gamer loyalty from the perspective of the theory of consumption values. *Decision Support Systems*, 114, 49-60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2018.08.007>
- Wang, W., Cao, D., & Ameen, N. (2023). Understanding customer satisfaction of augmented reality in retail: A human value orientation and consumption value perspective. *Information Technology & People*, 36(6), 2211–2233. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITP-04-2021-0293>